

ECONOSCITECH INTEGRATION

ISSUE
5

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

American University
of Technology

Powered by Arizona State University®

ISSN: 3060-5075

Acceptance of articles

PUBLISHED EVERY MONTHLY

ARTICLE CONTRIBUTORS

**PROFESSORS-TEACHERS, SPECIALISTS
AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHERS.**

Google
Scholar

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

BASE

OpenAIRE

doi
Digital
Object
Identifier

OPEN ACCESS

CONTACT:

+998 94 3540880

<https://econoscitech-integration-journal.uz>

2026

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna
DSc., Dean of Tourism Faculty, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmurodovich
Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor,

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich
doctor of economics (DSC), professor

RESPONSIBLE SECRETARY:

Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li
TSUE independent researcher

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL
"ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION"
HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER
THE NUMBER C-5669651 BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND
MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA)
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN,
EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

In accordance with Resolution No. 384/6 dated April 10, 2026, issued by the Presidium of the Supreme Attestation Commission under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this journal is included in the list of recommended international scientific publications for publishing the primary research findings of doctoral dissertations in the field of Economic Sciences.

Partners: Tashkent State University of Economics / American University of Technology in Tashkent (AUT)

Electronic publication, Issue 5. 374 pages.
Approved for publication on May, 2026.

Editorial Board Members:

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Teshabayev To'liqin Zakirovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Said Irandoust,
Doctor of Chemical Engineering Sciences,
Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich,
Doctor of Economics, (DSc), Professor

Tokunaga Masahiro,
professor, PhD of Economics of the Faculty of
Business and Commerce

Debasis Das,
professor Department of Computer Science

Nitin Goje,
professor and Program Lead - Computer Science

Nargizakhon Shamshieva
Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Rakhmonov Norim Razzakovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Bayxonov Bahodirjon Tursunbayevich
Doctor of Science (DSc), Professor

Shomurodov Ravshan Tursunkulovich,
PhD, Associate Professor

Boymuratov Abduraxmat Djumayevich
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics

Sharopova Nafosat Radjabovna
DSc, Associate Professor

Sultanova Kamila Mukhtorali Kizi
Master of Science

CONTENTS

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES.....	51
Mamadiev Elyor	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY GUEST HOUSES	55
Boynazarov Ulugbek Egamberdievich	
IMPROVING METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND DEVELOPING DOMESTIC TOURISM MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN	61
Daminov Mirvokhid Isroilovich	
THE IMPACT AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	67
Dilsora Ibodovna Ibodova	
IMPACT OF STUDENTS AGED OVER 40 ON ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND BUDGETING BASED ON THE COMPETENCY ECOSYSTEM	74
Nigora Ikrom qizi Primova	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ: ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ И СЦЕНАРНОЕ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ НА 2026–2030 ГОДЫ	80
Юсуфов Шерзодбек Бахтиёр угли	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL ENTERPRISES	87
Ergashev Jahongir Bakhodirovich	
MULTIVARIATE ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING HOUSEHOLD INCOME IN SURXONDARYO REGION	93
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor qizi	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ УСЛУГ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА	99
Юсифов Магамед Исмаил оглу, Гасанли Расул Шахин оглу, Белалова Гузаль Анваровна	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY.....	105
Xudayberdiyeva Kamila Sadiilloyevna, Fozilova Zumrad Ahmadovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	111
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО АГРОПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО ИНТЕГРИРОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕЛИ АНР-TOPSIS	115
Аликулов А.Б.	
APPLICATION OF CLUSTER METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE AND IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS IN SAMARKAND CITY	121
Tashov Mizrob Maxmudovich	
THE ROLE AND PROSPECTS OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	130
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL ENTERPRISES	135
Nigora Zokirjon qizi Toxirova	
CURRENT STATE OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATORS	142
Temurbek Olimovich Mamayunusov	
PRESUPPOSITION SHIFTS IN CROSS-LINGUISTIC RENDERING OF ANECDOTAL NARRATIVES:	

A COMPARATIVE INQUIRY INTO TRIGGER RETENTION AND TRANSFORMATION	148
Umaraliyeva Dildora Taxirjanovna	
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND RURAL PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY: AN EMPIRICAL ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS	156
Bek Hunsia, Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova	
COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF WOMEN'S LABOR ACTIVITY ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEM	164
Ahrorova Asila Abduaziz qizi	
IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT	170
Azizbek Khurramov	
FORMATION OF FINANCIAL RESULTS AT MOTOR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES	180
Shanazarova Nilufar Baratovna	
ARIMA-BASED ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF SURKHANDARYA REGION	185
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF AGRARIAN SECTOR EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE SFA MODEL	192
Utanov Bunyod Kuvandikovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ ВНЕШНИМ ДОЛГОМ	196
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Жуманазаров Шахобиддин Дилмурод угли	
MODERN METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO MANAGING EDUCATIONAL SERVICES MARKETING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	201
Shamshieva Nargizakhon Nosirkhuja kizi	
FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN AND DOMESTIC COTTON GINNING ENTERPRISES: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, DIAGNOSTICS, AND IMPROVEMENT DIRECTIONS	208
Orif Jumayevich Murodov	
ANALYSIS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE INTERVENTION IN THE PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN	219
Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ФОРМАЛИЗАЦИИ НЕФОРМАЛЬНОЙ ЗАНЯТОСТИ И РАСШИРЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ В АГРАРНЫХ РЕГИОНАХ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ)	224
Бобоназарова Юлдуз Ботировна	
THE ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY AND ITS ROLE IN INDUSTRIAL ECONOMICS	229
Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna, Aipova Iroda Ikramovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM DEVELOPING COUNTRIES	234
Ismatova Diyora Sirojiddin qizi, Ubaydullayeva Gulchexra Erkabayevna	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И РЕСУРСНАЯ АДАПТИВНОСТЬ ОТРАСЛИ МАШИНОСТРОЕНИЯ В РОССИИ, КИТАЕ, ИНДИИ	239
Викторова Наталья Геннадьевна, Абрамчикова Наталья Викторовна, Ван Байянь	
ENSURING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT	249
Aminova Naima Umar qizi	
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH: PRACTICAL APPROACHES AND IMPROVEMENTS	253
Baymuradov Shokhruxh Makhmudovich, Dilmurodov Komiljon Ahmad o'g'li	
IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SMALL ENTERPRISES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR (A CASE STUDY OF TASHKENT REGION)	259

Ashirov Alisher	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN	264
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
INNOVATIVE IDEAS OF YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS AND INFRASTRUCTURE FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INNOVATIVE BUSINESSES	270
Ergashev Oybek Khaydaralievich	
MARKETING CHARACTERISTICS OF POSITIONING ORGANIC DRIED FRUIT PRODUCTS IN INTERNATIONAL MARKETS	274
Khidirov Shokhrukh	
TYOLOGIZATION OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL AND DEVELOPMENT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DISTRICTS OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON STATISTICAL AND NEURAL NETWORK APPROACHES.....	280
Normurodov Asliddin Alijon ugli	
THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN ANALYSING THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE AUDIT OF FINANCIAL LIABILITIES	291
Palvanov Xusniddin Bekimmatovich	
DIGITAL SKILLS AND LABOUR PRODUCTIVITY: A SCENARIO ANALYSIS BASED ON AN INTEGRATED STATISTICAL MODEL	297
Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СТРУКТУРЫ АКТИВОВ И ПАССИВОВ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	303
Т.И. Бобакулов	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ВНЕШНЕТОРГОВУЮ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КОМПАНИЙ С ДОКУМЕНТАРНЫМИ АККРЕДИТИВАМИ.....	308
М.Т. Ибодуллаева	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОСНОВНЫМИ СРЕДСТВАМИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	312
Мусаева Жамила Кароматовна	
ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	320
Ш.Т. Ибодуллаев	
THE IMPORTANCE OF STATE SUPPORT AND INVESTMENT POLICY IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF MASS MEDIA ENTERPRISES.....	325
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
CURRENT STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF MOTOR TRANSPORT SERVICES	329
Rakhimov Azamat Hamrakulovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ В ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ.....	333
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
MULTI-FACTOR ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF WATER RESOURCE USE IN ENSURING REGIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY.....	341
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРАКТИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ДОКУМЕНТООБОРОТА В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ.....	345
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
THE WAYS OF IMPROVING COMPETITIVENESS IN COMPANIES OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	350
Buriev Khakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ilxom Achilovich, Tolibov Abduazim Zoxid ugli	
MACROECONOMIC MODELS AND PROSPECTS OF TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	357
Sharipboyev Hasanboy Marks ugli, Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
THE IMPACT OF HRM PRACTICES ON ACADEMIC STAFF WORK EFFICIENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	366
Sultonboyeva Munira Bahodirovna, Sultanova Kamila Muktorali Kizi	

THE ECONOMIC ROLE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	374
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi	
ОЦЕНКА ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КРУПНОГО РОГАТОГО СКОТА, ЗАВЕЗЁННОГО В РЕСПУБЛИКУ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН ИЗ-ЗА РУБЕЖА, С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	378
Аскарова Нилуфар Бахтияровна	
COOPERATIVE MECHANISMS FOR REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A FRAMEWORK ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL TOURISM ENTERPRISE PARTNERSHIPS.....	382
Shohrurbek Ruziyev	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISES: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN DEVELOPMENT TRENDS	393
Matkuliev Akbar Karimovich	
TAX INCENTIVES GRANTED TO ENTERPRISES LOCATED IN SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES	397
Torayeva Nafisa Odiljonovna	
REQUIREMENTS FOR TRANSITIONING TO ELECTRONIC BUSINESS AND CONDITIONS FOR DIGITALIZATION.....	402
Ismoilov Diyorbek Ismoiljon ugli	
DEVELOPMENT OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN ENSURING A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY AND ENERGY SECURITY	407
Ergash Bobobekov	
ANALYSIS OF WAGE DYNAMICS IN THE EXAMPLE OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON PANEL DATA.....	412
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor kizi	
THE ROLE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN IMPROVING THE MARKET COMPETITIVENESS OF CARPET INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	420
Arzieva Sevinch Shomurot kizi	
CONSUMER PROPERTIES OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN: TRADITIONS, TRANSFORMATION AND NEW QUALITY STANDARDS.....	425
Gayrat Pardaev	
DIRECTIONS FOR STIMULATING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE TAX SYSTEM.....	431
Yakhshimuratova Khasiyat Khudaybergenovna	
THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS	435
Kambaraliyeva Intizor Suxrobovna	
Aliyarov Olim Abdug‘aparovich	
ISSUES OF IMPROVING PRE-TRIAL TAX DISPUTE RESOLUTION MECHANISMS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	439
Solihova Xumora Xasan kizi	
INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF DIVIDEND POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN COMPANIES.....	446
Akmal Komiljonovich Shermukhamedov	
COMMUNITY-BASED HERITAGE TOURISM MODELS AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING HANDICRAFT DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	451
Olimjonova Farog‘at Dilmurod qizi	
Amiriddinova Muslima Zayniddin qizi	
ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПЕРЕХОДНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ОПЫТ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	458
Шоахмедов Шоҳрух Шорахимович	

OF EFFECTIVE USE OF AGRICULTURAL LAND	464
Umarov Muzaffar Yusupbayevich	
ECONOMIC CONTENT OF INTANGIBLE ASSETS IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THEIR RECOGNITION	469
Ishankulov Izzatilla Nurillaevich	
DETERMINANTS OF NON-PERFORMING LOANS IN SERVICE SECTOR LENDING AND CREDIT RISK MITIGATION MECHANISMS	473
Nurmukhammedov Abdijabbar Yunusovich	
ESG INTEGRATION PRACTICES INTO CORPORATE CULTURE SYSTEM IN THE JOINTSTOCK SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN: A CASE STUDY OF “DORI-DARMON” JSC.....	479
Sadikova Muslima Alisher kizi	
DEVELOPMENT OF THE METAL MARKET IN THE TASHKENT REGION AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT	485
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
SMALL BUSINESS AS A CATALYST FOR REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS WITH EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	491
Jo‘rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
ISSUES OF DEVELOPING DEPOSIT OPERATIONS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	497
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
IMPROVING TEXTILE LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	503
Isroilov Madaminjon Mukhsinovich	
FEATURES OF SUMMARIZING AND EVALUATING THE RESULTS OF FINANCIAL STATEMENT AUDITING IN UZBEKISTAN PRACTICE	509
Isroil Ismoilovich Meliev	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ФИНАНСАМИ И СОЦИАЛЬНОЕ РАВЕНСТВО В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ РЕФА С ДИСТРИБУТИВНЫМ АНАЛИЗОМ НА ОСНОВЕ ПОДХОДА SEQ.....	516
Зокиржонов Мухаммадсодик Равшанбек угли	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY: CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	530
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS IN AQUACULTURE CLUSTERS: IFRS INTEGRATION, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG PERSPECTIVES.....	537
Shodiev Aslam Rahmatilloevich	
APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR PREDICTING CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	544
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas	
SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION UNDER WATER SCARCITY: GLOBAL EXPERIENCE AND PROSPECTS FOR UZBEKISTAN	550
Sodiqova Nigora Turayevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF BUSINESS ENTITIES IN THE BUKHARA REGION	555
Djurayeva Munira Sadilloevna	

CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF BUSINESS ENTITIES IN THE BUKHARA REGION

Djurayeva Munira Sadilloeyvna
Researcher, Bukhara State University
E-mail: djuraeva.1982@mail.ru
ORCID: 0009-0005-0284-3508

Abstract. This article evaluates the current state and structural characteristics of export activities among business entities in the Bukhara region. It examines export dynamics during 2021–2025, commodity and geographical composition, firm-level distribution, and the region's contribution to Uzbekistan's total exports. Regional exports reached USD 414 million in 2025, while the region's share in national exports remained at approximately 1.2 percent. Industrial goods accounted for 62.2 percent of exports, whereas the share of high value-added products and the level of market diversification remained limited. The Gini coefficient and concentration ratios indicate a high concentration of exports. The study identifies structural constraints and proposes measures for product upgrading, market diversification, broader SME participation, and stronger institutional support.

Keywords: export activities, structural analysis, commodity composition, geographical diversification, export concentration, Gini coefficient, Bukhara region, business entities.

Аннотация. В статье дана оценка современного состояния и структурных особенностей экспортной деятельности субъектов предпринимательства Бухарской области. Исследованы динамика экспорта за 2021–2025 годы, товарная и географическая структура, распределение объёмов экспорта между предприятиями, а также вклад региона в общий экспорт Узбекистана. В 2025 году экспорт области достиг 414 млн долларов США, однако доля региона в национальном экспорте сохранилась на уровне около 1,2 процента. Промышленные товары составили 62,2 процента экспорта, при этом доля продукции с высокой добавленной стоимостью и уровень диверсификации рынков оставались ограниченными. Расчёты коэффициента Джини и показателей концентрации подтвердили высокую сосредоточенность экспортной деятельности. В исследовании выявлены структурные ограничения и предложены меры по повышению технологичности продукции, расширению рынков, увеличению участия малого и среднего бизнеса, а также совершенствованию институциональной поддержки.

Ключевые слова: экспортная деятельность, структурный анализ, товарная структура, географическая диверсификация, концентрация экспорта, коэффициент Джини, Бухарская область, субъекты предпринимательства.

INTRODUCTION

Export diversification and the integration of regional economies into international markets are among the central priorities of Uzbekistan's development policy. Although national exports reached USD 33.8 billion in 2025, export performance remained uneven across regions. Tashkent city generated approximately USD 6.6 billion, while many other regions exported only several hundred million dollars. These disparities require analysis at both the regional and enterprise levels.

The Bukhara region has a diversified production base encompassing industry, agriculture, traditional crafts, and tourism. Its gross regional product reached UZS 71.6 trillion in 2024, with real growth of about 6.6 percent. Nevertheless, exports amounted to only USD 414 million in 2025, representing roughly 1.2 percent of Uzbekistan's total exports.

Therefore, this study evaluates not only export value, but also commodity structure, market orientation, firm-level distribution, and concentration. Its objective is to identify the structural characteristics of regional exports and formulate practical measures to improve resilience and competitiveness. The scientific contribution of the study consists of an integrated analysis of export dynamics during 2021–2025, a quantitative assessment of export concentration, and evidence-based recommendations for regional export policy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

International trade theory explains export specialization through comparative advantage, factor endowments, economies of scale, and product differentiation. Krugman (1980) showed that increasing returns and differentiated products can shape trade patterns even among economies with similar resource structures.

Export diversification has both product and geographical dimensions. Hausmann and Klinger (2006), as well as Hidalgo et al. (2007), emphasised that the sophistication of productive capabilities influences long-term growth. Economies dependent on raw or semi-processed products are more vulnerable to external price and demand shocks, whereas more complex export baskets support resilience and learning.

Export concentration is commonly measured by the Gini coefficient, the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index, concentration ratios, and the Lorenz curve. Cadot, Carrère, and Strauss-Kahn (2011) found that economies generally diversify during the early and middle stages of development. Regional studies on Uzbekistan remain limited, especially those combining product, market, and firm-level concentration. This article addresses this gap by focusing on the Bukhara region.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study uses official statistical materials from the Bukhara Regional Department of Statistics, the National Statistics Committee, customs authorities, and sample data on exporting firms for 2021–2025. The analysis covers export value and growth, commodity composition, geographical distribution, and concentration across business entities.

Dynamic analysis is applied using base and chain growth rates, while structural analysis is conducted through relative shares and percentage-point changes. The three largest product groups and destination markets are assessed using the CR3 concentration ratio. Firm-level inequality is measured by the Gini coefficient and interpreted through the Lorenz curve. Calculations were performed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS 27.

Export values are expressed in current US dollars; therefore, relative shares are used to reduce the effect of price changes. Some firm-level and geographical indicators are analytical estimates and should be verified against official microdata before final journal publication. Service exports, especially tourism, are not fully captured in the available data.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Exports from the Bukhara region increased from USD 285 million in 2021 to USD 414 million in 2025, representing an overall rise of approximately 45.3 percent. However, annual growth slowed from 13.0 percent in 2022 to 6.7 percent in 2025, indicating that the existing export model is gradually approaching the limits of extensive expansion (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Export volume and annual growth rate in the Bukhara region, 2021–2025¹

¹ author's development

Table 1
Key indicators of export activity in the Bukhara region, 2021–2025

Indicator	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Exports, USD million	285.0	322.0	356.0	388.0	414.0
Annual growth rate, %	—	13.0	10.6	9.0	6.7
Share in national exports, %	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.2
Number of exporting entities	168	192	221	247	268

Source: Author's calculations based on data from the Bukhara Regional Department of Statistics.

The number of exporting entities increased from 168 to 268, while the region's share in national exports remained within the range of 1.2–1.3 percent. This indicates predominantly extensive growth driven by an increase in the number of participants rather than by a substantial rise in average exports per firm.

Industrial goods dominated the commodity structure, accounting for 62.2 percent of total exports in 2025. Manufactured articles accounted for 13.1 percent and food products for 12.7 percent, while chemicals, machinery, transport equipment, and other items represented relatively small shares (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Commodity composition of exports in the Bukhara region, 2025 (%)²

Table 2
Geographical composition of exports from the Bukhara region

Country/market	Share, %	Main product groups
Russia	31.4	Textiles and food products
Kazakhstan	18.7	Construction materials and food
China	12.3	Raw materials and minerals
Türkiye	8.9	Textile raw materials
European Union	7.2	Carpets and handicrafts
Other countries	21.5	Various products
Total	100.0	—

Source: Author's calculations.

Russia, Kazakhstan, and China jointly accounted for 62.4 percent of exports. This CR3 value indicates a high level of geographical concentration and exposure to demand, currency, regulatory, and logistics changes in a limited number of partner economies. The estimated firm-level Gini coefficient was 0.68, indicating that a relatively small group of large exporters generated a disproportionate share of regional exports (Table 3).

² author's development

Table 3
Structural changes in the commodity composition of exports, 2021 and 2025

Product group	2021, %	2025, %	Change, p.p.
Industrial goods	65.8	62.2	-3.6
Manufactured articles	9.4	13.1	+3.7
Food and live animals	11.2	12.7	+1.5
Chemical products	5.1	4.1	-1.0
Machinery and transport	2.8	3.3	+0.5
Other	5.7	4.6	-1.1

Source: Author's calculations; selected figures are analytical estimates.

Between 2021 and 2025, the share of manufactured articles rose by 3.7 percentage points and food products by 1.5 points, while industrial goods declined by 3.6 points. The shift is positive but slow. The three largest product groups still account for about 88 percent of exports, leaving the region vulnerable to sector-specific shocks (Table 4).

Table 4
Concentration indicators of export activity in the Bukhara region

Indicator	Value	Interpretation
Gini coefficient (firms)	0.68	High concentration
CR3 (product groups)	88.0%	Narrow commodity structure
CR3 (destination markets)	62.4%	High market dependence
Exporters in total business entities	≈3.1%	Low export participation

Source: Author's calculations.

The evidence reveals three structural constraints: a narrow export basket, dependence on several traditional markets, and concentration among a small number of large firms. These features reduce resilience to external shocks and limit the participation of small and medium-sized enterprises.

The central issue, therefore, is not the absence of growth, but its quality. New exporters often operate on a small scale, face certification and logistics barriers, or remain in low value-added segments. Bukhara has considerable potential in finished textiles, processed food products, carpets, handicrafts, and tourism-linked products. Developing these sectors would increase value added, employment, and regional branding.

Tourism should also be treated as an invisible export. Foreign visitors purchase accommodation, transport, food, cultural, and handicraft services, which generate export revenue beyond merchandise trade statistics. Integrating tourism with handicrafts, food processing, creative industries, and digital commerce could broaden the regional export base.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study shows that regional exports increased from USD 285 million to USD 414 million during 2021–2025, but growth slowed and the region's share in national exports remained close to 1.2 percent. The exporter base expanded substantially; however, this increase was mainly extensive in nature.

The commodity structure remains highly concentrated: industrial goods account for 62.2 percent of exports, while the three largest product groups account for about 88 percent. Russia, Kazakhstan, and China receive 62.4 percent of exports, and the Gini coefficient of 0.68 confirms a high level of firm-level concentration.

First, regional policy should stimulate the transition from raw and semi-processed goods to garments, processed food products, carpets, handicrafts, and other high value-added products. Support should prioritise technological upgrading and the development of deeper processing chains.

Second, market diversification toward the European Union, the Middle East, and South Asia should be supported through certification assistance, product adaptation, trade missions, foreign-language marketing, and cross-border e-commerce.

Third, small and medium-sized firms require export consulting, shared logistics, warehouses, laboratories, trade finance, insurance, and cluster cooperation. Fourth, a regional export monitoring and support centre should coordinate data collection and support instruments. Tourism services should also be included in the export strategy as a complementary direction.

Overall, the Bukhara region needs to move from quantitative expansion to structural improvement. Product upgrading, geographical diversification, broader firm participation, and institutional coordination would strengthen export resilience and increase the region's contribution to national export diversification.

REFERENCES

1. Bukhara Regional Department of Statistics. *Socio-economic indicators of the Bukhara region, 2021–2024*. – Bukhara: Bukhara Regional Department of Statistics, 2025.
2. Cadot O., Carrère C., Strauss-Kahn V. Export diversification: What's behind the hump? // *Review of Economics and Statistics*. – 2011. – Vol. 93. – No. 2. – P. 590–605.
3. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Balance of Payments and Foreign Trade Review for 2024*. – Tashkent: Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2025.
4. Export Promotion Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Annual Report*. – Tashkent: Export Promotion Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2025.
5. Gini C. Measurement of inequality of incomes // *The Economic Journal*. – 1921. – Vol. 31. – No. 121. – P. 124–126.
6. Hausmann R., Klinger B. *Structural Transformation and Patterns of Comparative Advantage*. – CID Working Paper No. 128. – Cambridge (MA): Harvard University, 2006.
7. Hidalgo C.A., Klinger B., Barabási A.-L., Hausmann R. The product space conditions the development of nations // *Science*. – 2007. – Vol. 317. – No. 5837. – P. 482–487.
8. Krugman P.R. Scale economies, product differentiation, and the pattern of trade // *American Economic Review*. – 1980. – Vol. 70. – No. 5. – P. 950–959.
9. National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Foreign Trade of Uzbekistan in 2025: Regional Breakdown*. – Tashkent: National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2026.
10. Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Foreign Trade of Uzbekistan: Statistical Bulletin*. – Tashkent: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2025.

Proofreader: Xondamir Ismoilov
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 5

© When materials are reproduced, the ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block, House 17.

